

Deliverable
D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.5
Workpackage 6

Responsible Partner: 2-AGES, 23-UoS

Description of the task

The deliverable **D-JRP15-FED-AMR-WP6.5** (*Main code for the mathematical modelling made available in public repository (e.g. GitHub) with associated documentation (which can be used as "Material and Method" section of the forthcoming publications)*) ensures that the modelling work on microbial communities will be transparent and reproducible in line with Open Science philosophy.

This deliverable relates to WP6 task 2, 'Modelling microbial communities', and describes prototype code written in Python, along with associated documentation, uploaded to online repository GitLab for version control purposes. The codes are actually constantly updated following major changes.

Description of the deliverable

There are two repositories that Dr Gardner maintains on GitHub: the first for mathematical modelling and analysis, and the second to generate in-silico time-series microbial abundance data. Please find description for this deliverable as follows:

Git repositories:

<https://github.com/BCGardner/lotka-volterra.git>

This first repository explores the use of the generalised Lotka-Volterra set of equations to predict the dynamics of microbial communities in the gut microbiome. Ridge regression as used in [1], and Bayesian linear regression, are some of the methods used to infer model parameters from time-series metagenomic data. The time-series data used for this analysis has been taken from public available repositories, for example from [1], or has been generated using agent-based modelling as described in [2, 3]. The goal here is to build on these methods and predict the long-term stability of these microbial communities in response to external perturbation factors.

https://github.com/BCGardner/sglv_timeseries.git

This second repository is a fork of [3], and is used to generate in-silico agent-based microbial time-series data. This repository extends [3] by including the impact of external perturbation.

Draft of the methods, findings and general research progress is also updated on overleaf in a paper format:

<https://www.overleaf.com/project/62011b386dcfe37405750c0d>

[1] Stein, R. R., Bucci, V., Toussaint, N. C., Buffie, C. G., Räscher, G., Pamer, E. G., Sander, C., & Xavier, J. B. (2013). Ecological Modeling from Time-Series Inference: Insight into Dynamics and Stability of Intestinal Microbiota. *PLoS Computational Biology*, 9(12), 31–36. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1003388>

[2] Descheemaeker, L. and de Buyl, S. (2020). Stochastic logistic models reproduce experimental time series of microbial communities, *eLife*, 9, pp. 1–15. doi: 10.7554/eLife.55650.

[3] https://github.com/lanadescheemaeker/sglv_timeseries.git

Confidentiality of the documents

These two repositories are private, but we can grant access to the FED-AMR team on request.